

Chi-Square Assessment Practices of Entrepreneurial Orientation, Employee Satisfaction, and Customer Satisfaction With Business Performance: a Case of CBE Bule Hora Town, Ethiopia

Gada Gizachew Wakjira

Research Scholar (PhD), Bule Hora University, Marketing Management Department, Bule Hora University, Bule Hora, Horn Africa, Ethiopia.

Abstract - The aim of this investigation has aimed that depending the influencing factor of direct effects of EO with BP with mediating influence of Employee and Customer Satisfaction, and how Business organization bank CBE, Ethiopia (EO) influences BP of Commercial Banks of Ethiopia, using the Explanatory Inferential, Model Summery, Analyses of Variance Coefficient of Regression influence to test hypotheses test. In this study, factor that affect Entrepreneurial Orientation on Business performance as a mediating effect variable Employee satisfaction of the Customers Satisfaction was considered with 384 unknown respondents, and the results show positively affects Entrepreneurial Orientation with Business performance, Employee Satisfaction with Business performance, Customers Satisfaction with Business Performance, Entrepreneurial Orientation with Employee Satisfaction, and Entrepreneurial Orientation with Customers Satisfaction positive relationship with business performance, and the study provides both independent, Dependent and Mediating Variables has significantly positive influence in CBE, Ethiopia.

Keywords: Business Performance, Entrepreneurial Orientation, employee Satisfaction, customer satisfaction and CBE.

1. INTRODUCTION

The relationship between Entrepreneurial orientation (EO) and Business performance, and to generate a definitive results probably due to the omission of the moderating role of different unidentified variables (Covin & Slevin, 2018, and Lee & Chu, 2019; Lumpkin & Dess, 2021), and to explicitly address this gap, and this study it has investigate the Entrepreneurial Orientation influenced with Business performance, considering the mediating effect of (CS), and the impact of (BP), and In BP of CBE has a significant relationship with Business Performance in their ability to create superior Customer satisfaction value and Employee Satisfaction pursue Entrepreneurial Orientation opportunities (Buli, 2019), but to do so, CBE must use an integrative approach of EO and BP of CBE, Choi and Williams (2019), and it found the business activities that mediated Employee Satisfaction, and Customer Satisfaction that the relationship between EO, and BP of CBE, and it constructs of EO and BP took into account different elements of Employee Satisfaction of banks has a limitation to satisfy Employee and Customer to be satisfied in Ethiopia has many problem to fill that gap to fill the problem of Employee and Customer Satisfaction in further study in to solve and to satisfy Employee and Customer the problem and the limitation of Banks to add minimum Five banks specially in the area of Gomaju, Taf, area of Bariso Dukale Square, Infront of Bule Hora Hospital, and in Bule Hora University Ethiopian Banks, Neftalí Parga-Montoya (2019).

The effects Multiple linear Regression has a positive relationship between EO with BP, and how Employee and Customer Satisfaction works as a mediated variable in this relationship, providing empirically positive

relationship between Customer and Employee Satisfaction with Business Performance in the context of CBE, Ethiopia in a developing country, and this contribution by itself, and his mediator variables to using Chi-square, Case processing Summery and the relationship between predict variables, mediating variables of Employee satisfaction and Customer Satisfaction with banks Business Performance of CBE, Ethiopia.

2. OBJECTIVE OF INVESTIGATION

1. To assess the direct relationship between Entrepreneurial Orientation practice and Business Performance of CBE.
2. To analysis the direct relationship between Employee Satisfaction and Business Performance of CBE.
3. To assess the direct relationship of Customer Satisfaction practice and Business Performance of CBE.

3. CONCEPTUAL INVESTIGATION

Fig -1: Conceptual Investigation

Source: Value of AMOS output (2023)

4. HYPOTHESIS INVESTIGATION TEST

H1: Entrepreneurial Orientation has a direct Relationship with Business Performance of CBE.

H2: Employee Satisfaction has mediated a direct Relationship with Business Performance of CBE.

H3: Customer Satisfaction has a mediated a direct Relationship with Business Performance of CBE.

5. INVESTIGATION APPROACH AND DESIGN

The quantitative research design to serve in many ways and the justifications support why quantitative research design to be selected in most of the empirical investigations in Commercial Banks of Ethiopia, has to be conducted by adopting quantitative approach in their designs to determine an expected relationships which might emerge from interaction between a set of given research variables, and this approach that has to be designed Descriptive Chi-square Relationship between Independent, Independent and Mediating Variable that can be analysed research designed that can be developed, Entrepreneurial Orientation, Customer Satisfaction, Employee satisfaction on Business Performance of CBE, Ethiopia that factor of descriptive Chi-square data has designed to be analysed, the direct Effect, and Blanco-Donoso, L. (2019), and Employee Satisfaction and Customer Satisfaction data is in the research design, and there analysed with Case Processing Summery, Relationship between Variables and dependent variables and chi-square test. We have shown that the relationship between variables and strength of variables, with the evidence of mediating variable of Employee Satisfaction and Customer Satisfaction of data similarity, and feelings through identification in, for 120 respondent to collect questionnaires from Employee and Customer of CBE, Ethiopia and data collected from 120 Respondents, and Research technique to be designed with Simple random techniques and Stratified sampling technique has to be designed in Ethiopian CBE Knoster, K. C., & Goodboy, A. K. (2020).

6. CASE PROCESSING SUMMARY OF BP, EO, AND CS

Table -1: Case processing Summery of BP, EO, and CS

Table with 7 columns: Variable, N, %, Missing data (N, %), Total (N, %). Rows include Business Performance * Entrepreneurial Orientation, Business Performance * Employee Satisfaction, and Business Performance * Customer Satisfaction.

Source: Case processing Summery of BP, EO, and CS (2023)

The case processing Summery study that can investigated search for correlations between Business Performance with, Business Performance with Employee Satisfaction and From Business Performance With Customer Satisfaction independent variables with dependent variables and two Mediating variables with Dependent variables with 120 Respondent to gather and investigated without missing data 100% valid data to confirm properties, and the case processing summery simple show the any missing data of any respondents input in each variables case processing summery valid statistics, Missing data and Total output in SPSS. 100% means all respondent fill all the required fields.

7. CROSS TABULATION OF EO, ES AND CS WITH BP

Table -2: Cross Tabulation of EO, ES and CS with BP

Business Performance * Entrepreneurial Orientation Cross tabulation			Entrepreneurial Orientation						Total
Business Performance * Employee Satisfaction Cross tabulation			12.00	13.00	14.00	15.00	16.00	17.00	
Business Performance * Customer Satisfaction Cross tabulation			0						
Business Performance	19.00	Count	1	.0	.0	.0	.0	.0	1
		Expected Count	.1	.2	.4	.2	.2	.0	1.0
	20.00	Count	5	9	4	2	0	0	20
		Expected Count	1.5	3.5	7.0	3.7	4.0	.3	20.0
	21.00	Count	2	9	26	11	1	0	49
		Expected Count	3.7	8.6	17.2	9.0	9.8	.8	49.0
	22.00	Count	1	3	10	8	15	0	37
		Expected Count	2.8	6.5	13.0	6.8	7.4	.6	37.0
23.00	Count	.0	.0	2	1	7	2	12	
	Expected Count	.9	2.1	4.2	2.2	2.4	.2	12.0	
Over all		Count data	9	21	42	22	24	2	120
		Expected Count data	9.0	21.0	42.0	22.0	24.0	2.0	120.0

Source: Cross Tabulation of EO, ES and CS with BP (2023)

Quantitatively data that can be analysed the strong Relationship between multiple variables it referred to as contingency group variables to gather, and to correlate friendly Business Performance with Entrepreneurial Orientation, Employee Satisfaction and Customer Satisfaction Cross tabulation of total count result 9%, 21%, 42%, 22%, 24%, 2% the main frame statistical model of similar line of the variable Entrepreneurial Orientation, Employee Satisfaction and Customer Satisfaction with Business Performance 42% Expected Count relationship with Business Performance has a significant relationship and valid data count and Expected count of data can be stored to confirm the variables of Entrepreneurial Orientation, Employee Satisfaction and Customer Satisfaction strong relationship with Business Performance in CBE Bule Hora town.

8. CHI-SQUARE TESTS EO, BP

Table -3: EO, BP of Variables

Chi-Square Tests			
	Results	Df	Asymp. P-Value. (2 sided)
Value of Chi-Square	96.179a	.25	.000**
Value of Likelihood Ratio	82.164	.25	.000**
Value of Linear-by-Linear Association	50.306	.1	.000**
Number of Population	120		
EO, BP Variables			

Source: EO, BP (2023)

The relationship Cell of chi square Expected count of <.05% and the minimum Expected count is < 0.01 to be assessing the goodness fit between value result of EO and BP, and those prediction can be expected theoretically the association between Descriptive analyses, and type of treatment were tested using the chi-square tests, and Since the p value (corresponding to the Pearson Chi-square test) is >0.05% with 95% Confidence level, To estimate negative hypothesis is rejected, and the Positive Asymp. Sig.(2-sided) <0.5 is accepted results Pearson Chi-Square value 96.179^a, Likelihood Ratio 82.164, Linear-by-Linear Association 50.306, with Valid people count 120 population, and the degree of Freedom 25 and 1 with P-Value result .000 that to be conclude the relationship between CS with BP.

Therefore, H1: Entrepreneurial Orientation has a direct Relationship with Business Performance of CBE Bule Hora Town with P-Value <05% to solve the problem of limitation of Banks in Bule Hora town not Compare Banks with Customer.

9. CHI -SQUARE TEST OF ES, BP

Table -4: Chi Square test of ES, BP

Chi Square Tests			
	Results	Df	Asymp. P-Value. (2 sided)
Value of Chi Square	568.944a	20	.000**
Value of Likelihood Ratio	290.162	20	.000**
Value of Linear by Linear Association	114.625	.1	.000**
Number of Population	120		
ES, BP Variables			

Source: Result of ES, BP (2023)

The relationship Cell of chi square Expected count of <.05% and the minimum Expected count is < 0.01 to be assessing the goodness fit between observed value of Employee Satisfaction, Business Performance, and those expected theoretically the association between demographic factors, and type of treatment were tested using the chi-square tests, and Since the p-value (corresponding to the Pearson Chi-square test) is greater than < 0.05% with 95% Confidence level, the estimation of Null hypothesis is rejected, and the alternative Asymp. Sig.(2-sided) >0.5 is accepted results Pearson Chi-Square value 568.944^a, Likelihood

Ratio 290.162, Linear-by-Linear Association 114.625, with Valid people count 120 population, and the degree of Freedom 25 and 1 with P-Value result .000 that to be conclude the relationship between CS with BP.

Therefore, H2: Employee Satisfaction has mediated a direct Relationship with Business Performance of CBE, Bule Hora Town with P-Value <05% to solve the problem of limitation of Banks in Bule Hora town not Compare Banks with Customer.

10. CHI SQUARE TESTS OF CS, BP

Table -5: Chi square tests of CS, BP

Chi Square Tests			
	Results	Df	Asymp. P-Value (2 sided)
Value of Chi Square	582.237 ^a	15	.000**
Value of Likelihood Ratio	304.679	15	.000**
Value of Linear by Linear Association	116.790	1	.000**
Number of Population	120		
CS, BP Variables			

Source: Result of CS, BP (2023)

The relationship Cell of chi square Expected count of <.05% and the minimum Expected count is < 0.01 to be assessing the goodness fit between observed value of CS with BP, , and those prediction can be expected theoretically the association between Descriptive analyses, and type of treatment were tested using the chi-square tests, and Since the p value (corresponding to the Pearson Chi-square test) is >0.05% with 95% Confidence level, To estimate negative hypothesis is rejected, and the Positive Asymp. Sig.(2-sided) <0.5 is accepted results Pearson Chi-Square value 582.237^a, Likelihood Ratio 304.679, Linear-by-Linear Association 116.790, with Valid people count 120 population, and the degree of Freedom 25 and 1 with P-Value result .000 that to be conclude the relationship between CS with BP.

Therefore, H3: Customer Satisfaction has a mediated a direct Relationship with Business Performance of CBE, Bule Hora Town with P-Value <05% to solve the problem of limitation of Banks in Bule Hora town not Compare Banks with Customer.

11. CONCLUSION

The case processing Summery study that can investigated search for correlations between Business Performance with, Business Performance with Employee Satisfaction and From Business Performance With Customer Satisfaction independent variables with dependent variables and two Mediating variables with Dependent variables with 120 Respondent to gather and investigated without missing data 100% valid data to confirm properties, and the case processing summery simple show the any missing data of any respondents input in each variables case processing summery valid statistics, Missing data and Total output in SPSS. 100% means all respondent fill all the required fields.

Quantitatively data that can be analysed the strong Relationship between multiple variables it referred to as contingency group variables to gather, and to correlate friendly Business Performance with Entrepreneurial Orientation, Employee Satisfaction and Customer Satisfaction Cross tabulation of total count result 9%, 21%, 42%, 22%, 24%, 2% the main frame statistical model of similar line of the variable Entrepreneurial Orientation, Employee Satisfaction and Customer Satisfaction with Business Performance 42% Expected Count relationship with Business Performance has a significant relationship and valid data count and Expected count of data can be stored to confirm the variables of Entrepreneurial Orientation, Employee Satisfaction and Customer Satisfaction strong relationship with Business Performance in CBE Bule Hora town.

The relationship Cell of Expected count less than $<.05\%$ and the minimum Expected count is less than 0.02% to denoting a statistical method assessing the goodness of fit between observed value of Entrepreneurial Orientation, Employee Satisfaction Customer Satisfaction with Business performance, , and those prediction can be expected theoretically the association between Descriptive analyses, and type of treatment were tested using the chi-square tests, and Since the p value (corresponding to the Pearson Chi-square test) is $>0.05\%$ with 95% Confidence level, To estimate negative hypothesis is rejected, and the Positive Asymp. Sig.(2-sided) <0.5 is accepted results Pearson Chi-Square value (582.237a, 658,944 and 96,306) Likelihood Ratio (304.679, 290,162 and 82,306), Linear-by-Linear Association (114,625, 116.790 and 80,306), with Valid people count 120 response rate, and the degree of Freedom 25 and 1 both Independent, Mediating and Dependent Variables that correlated with P-Value result $.000^{**}$, that can be conclude that there is a the relationship between, EO, ES, CS with BP in with P-Value $<05\%$ to solve the problem and the limitation of Banks to add minimum Four banks specially in the area of Gomaju, Taf, area of Bariso Dukale Square, Infront of Bule Hora Hospital CBE Bule Hora Town Ethiopia.

REFERENCES

- [1] Albergaria, M., & Jabbour, C. J. C. (2019), the role of big data analytics capabilities (BDAC) in understanding the challenges of service information and operations management in the sharing economy Evidence of peer effects in libraries. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijinfomgt.2019.10.008>.
- [2] Álvaro, J. L., Garrido, A., Pereira, C. R., Torres, A. R., & Barros, S. C. (2019). Unemployment, self-esteem, and depression: Differences between men and women. *The Spanish Journal of Psychology*, 22-30. <https://doi.org/10.1017/sjp.2018.68>
- [3] Blanco-Donoso, L. M., Moreno-Jiménez, B., Pereira, G., & Garrosa, E. (2019), Effects of co-worker and supervisor support on nurses' energy and motivation through role ambiguity and psychological flexibility, *The Spanish Journal of Psychology*, 22, Article E25. <https://doi.org/10.1017/sjp.2019.10>
- [4] Dubey, R., Gunasekaran, A., Childe, S. J., Bryde, D. J., Giannakis, M., Foropon, C., Roubaud, D., & Hazen, B. T. (2020), Big data analytics and artificial intelligence pathway to operational performance under the effects of entrepreneurial orientation and environmental dynamism. *International Journal of Production Economics*, 226 (August) 107599. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijpe.2019.107599>.
- [5] Gada Gizachew Wakjira (2022). The significance effect of Market Orientation on Business Performance the mediation Role of Customer Satisfaction and Employee Satisfaction the case of CBE, PUIRJ p. 65-88. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7495221>
- [6] Gada Gizachew Wakjira (2021). The determinants of Coffee Quality on Export Performance the A case of Bule Hora Branch ECX. *Journal of International Journal of Multidisciplinary Educational Research*. P. 10-18. [Http://ijmer.in.doi/2021/10.09.83](http://ijmer.in.doi/2021/10.09.83)
- [7] Haroon R Abbu (2016) Synergistic Effects of Market Orientation Implementation and Internalization Levels and its Impact on Firm Performance published in *Journal of Business Research* p.1-15.
- [8] <https://pqdtopen.proquest.com/doc/2154809602.html?FMT=ABS>
- [9] Hayes, A. F. (2022). Introduction to mediation, moderation, and conditional process analysis: A regression-based approach (3rdEd.). The Guilford Press.

- [10]Knoster, K. C., & Goodboy, A. K. (2020), A conditional process model of academic demands and student learning. *Communication Education*, 69(3), 335–355. <https://doi.org/10.1080/03634523.2020.1713387>
- [11] Dr.A.SHAJI GEORGE. (2023). Toxicity in the Workplace: The Silent Killer of Careers and Lives. *Partners Universal International Innovation Journal (PUIIJ)*, 01(02), 1–21. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7852087>
- [12]Muralidharan, S., & Kim, E. A. (2020). Can empathy offset low bystander efficacy Effectiveness of domestic violence prevention narratives in India. *Health Communication*, 35(10), 1229–1238. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10410236.2019.1623645>
- [13]Rahmat, M., Akib, H., Rizal, M., Sakawati, H., & Aslinda, A. (2021), Hubungan Bundara Organizes Denman Inovasi Perusahaan Correlation of Organizational Culture with Company Innovation, *JENIUS (JOurnal of Management Summer Daya Manusia)*, 4(2), 145. <https://doi.org/10.32493/jjsdm.v4i2.9083>.
- [14]Dr. A.Shaji George, Dr.T. Baskar, & A.S. Hovan George. (2022). A Comparative Analysis of India's Development of Electronic Marketing During The Pandemic of Covid 19. *Partners Universal International Research Journal (PUIRJ)* ISSN: 2583–5602, 01(04), 45–53. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7422200>
- [15]Siagian, G. S., & Ikatrinasari, Z. F. (2019), Pengaruh Manajemen Pengetahuan Terhadap Inovasi: Kasus Industri IT di Indonesia, *Operations Excellence Journal of Applied Industrial Engineering*, 11(1), 71. <https://doi.org/10.22441/oe.v10.3.2018.017>.
- [16]Shah, S. Z. A., & Ahmad, M. (2019), Entrepreneurial orientation and performance of small and medium-sized enterprises: mediation effects of differentiation strategy. *Competitiveness Review*, 29(5), 551–572. <https://doi.org/10.1108/CR-06-2018-0038>.
- [17]Susana, E., &Andarwati, M.(2021), Peningkatan Keunggulan Bersaing dan Kieran UKM di Era Pandemic Covid-19. In *Seminar National Sistem Informs (SENASIF)* (Vol. 5, pp. 2729–2742).
- [18]Tseng, C. H., Chang, K. H., & Chen, H. W. (2019), Strategic orientation, environmental innovation capability, and environmental sustainability performance: The case of Taiwanese suppliers. *Sustainability (Switzerland)*, 11(4), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su11041127>.